

Environmental Sustainability Assessment of Innovative Materials for Wastewater Treatment Using Life Cycle Assessment

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Abstract

Background and Purpose:

This research forms part of the IN2AQUAS project (HORIZON-MSCA-2022-DN-01, Project: 101119555), which aims to apply Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodologies to assess and guide the environmental sustainability of innovative materials and processes for wastewater treatment. The study focuses on the synthesis and application of materials such as carbon quantum dots (CQDs), humic substances (HS), and humic-like substances (HLS). These materials are of growing interest because of their ability to enhance pollutant degradation through photochemical and adsorption processes. By quantifying their environmental footprints, the work aims to establish a framework to identify environmental trade-offs and optimize material development pathways.

Methods:

Primary experimental data collected within the IN2AQUAS consortium were used to construct detailed Life Cycle Inventories (LCIs) for the synthesis and application of selected materials. The LCA followed ISO 14040/44 standards and was implemented using the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) method in SimaPro software. Impact categories included energy use, emissions, and resource consumption, providing a multi-dimensional perspective on environmental performance.

Results:

Electricity consumption emerged as the dominant contributor across most impact categories, particularly under EU average energy conditions. Sensitivity analyses revealed that the carbon intensity of electricity significantly affects results, highlighting the influence of local energy systems. For chemical synthesis, reagents such as sodium hydroxide and the metal organic framework MIL-101-Fe were identified as substantial contributors to overall impacts.

Conclusions:

The results offer an early yet comprehensive understanding of the environmental implications of integrating innovative materials into wastewater treatment systems. Electricity and reagent production represent key environmental hotspots, emphasizing the need for cleaner energy integration, optimized process design, and material substitution strategies. The findings contribute to establishing sustainability-oriented criteria for future material development and pilot-scale evaluations.

Keywords

Environmental Impact; Life Cycle Assessment (LCA); Wastewater Treatment; Material Synthesis; Sustainability Assessment

INTRODUCTION

The present work builds on data from the IN2AQUAS network to conduct a preliminary but comprehensive LCA of selected materials, grape bagasse HLS extract, sewage sludge HLS extract, and coated polysulfone sheets, assessing both synthesis and use stages. The broader objective is to develop a data driven understanding of how early-stage material innovations interact with the environmental performance of wastewater treatment systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

LCA Framework:

The study followed ISO 14040/44 standards using SimaPro software for modelling. The ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) v1.08 method was applied, which covers 20 midpoint impact categories.

Goal and Scope

Objective: Assess the environmental impacts of synthesizing HLS grape bagasse extract, sewage sludge HLS extract, and polysulfone sheets for wastewater treatment applications. Also, the environmental impact of the use of the sewage sludge HLS extract for the removal of pollutants in a Photo Fenton process is analysed.

Further materials and technologies will be analysed when data is available.

The aspects investigated include:

- (1) The synthesis of HLS grape bagasse extract (functional unit: 1 kg of grape bagasse HLS extract)
- (2) The application of this extract in the Photo-Fenton process for wastewater treatment (functional unit: treatment of 1 litre of wastewater)
- (3) The synthesis of HLS extract derived from sewage sludge (functional unit: 1 kg of sewage sludge HLS extract)
- (4) The synthesis of coated polysulfone sheets (functional unit: 10 coated polysulfone sheets)

System Boundaries: "Cradle-to-grave" for synthesis and application processes.

Life Cycle Inventory

Primary data: laboratory experiments and collaborative exchanges within the IN2AQUAS consortium

Databases: Ecoinvent Centre (formerly Swiss Centre for Life Cycle Inventories)

Ecoinvent v.3.10 Database, 2024, database for background information.

Material Inputs: Quantified inputs include raw materials for the synthesis of the materials used for the wastewater treatment provided by the IN2AQUAS network candidates.

Impact Assessment Methodology

Methodology Used: ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint (H) V1.08/ World (2010) H.

Impact Categories Analysed: Global warming, Stratospheric ozone depletion, Ionizing radiation, Ozone formation, Human health, Fine particulate matter formation, Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems, Terrestrial acidification, Freshwater eutrophication, Marine eutrophication, Terrestrial ecotoxicity, Freshwater ecotoxicity, Marine ecotoxicity, Human carcinogenic toxicity, Human non-carcinogenic toxicity, Land use, Mineral resource scarcity, Fossil resource scarcity, Water consumption.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HLS Grape Bagasse Extract Synthesis

The LCA revealed the use of electricity as the main contributor in almost all impact categories. Focusing on Global Warming potential there was a contribution higher than 70% using an EU average electricity mix. Due to the high contribution of electricity, it was decided to see the results on the first and last EU country in terms of carbon intensity and compare.

It was confirmed that those extremes highly affected the impact of electricity. Sodium Hydroxide for the washing of the membranes used for the Grape Bagasse HLS Extract synthesis impacted second after electricity in terms of Global Warming Potential.

HLS Grape Bagasse Extract Photo Fenton Process

Electricity emerged as the main contributor in all impact categories for this process which was also tested with an EU average and the extreme examples of carbon intensity within the EU countries in terms of electricity mix. The electricity impact in Global Warming Potential reached a contribution even higher than 95%.

Sewage Sludge HLS Extract Synthesis

Like Grape bagasse we can also monitor electricity as the main contributor for most impact categories and the main contributor in terms of Global Warming Potential. We reach a contribution even higher than 65% for an electricity mix of EU average which is reduced and increased accordingly when applied for the electricity mix of the first and last EU country in terms of carbon footprint intensity.

Coated Polysulfone Flat Sheets Production

For the synthesis of the Coated Polysulfone Sheets the main contributors are more diverse between the use of certain chemicals and the use of water in most impact categories.

The synthesis of MIL-101-Fe which is a type of metal-organic framework can be spotted as the highest contributor in most impact categories. It is used for the coating of the polysulfone sheets reaching a contribution of close to 60% for Global Warming Potential.

Electricity is a minor contributor in this case.

Figure 1. Graph generated from SimaPro that visually demonstrates how each input contributes to each impact category for the production of 1kg of HLS Grape bagasse extract.

Integration with the Wastewater Treatment Context

These findings underline that while advanced materials offer promising functional improvements, their sustainability cannot be judged solely by treatment performance. For instance, if HLS based materials enable higher pollutant removal efficiency or lower chemical consumption at plant scale, their synthesis impacts could be offset by operational gains. Conversely, if their production is highly energy-intensive, these benefits may be diminished. Thus, the integration of LCA results into system level modelling will be essential to determine their net environmental value.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions are:

- 1) Electricity consumption dominates environmental impacts across synthesis and application stages, strongly influenced by the carbon intensity of local electricity mixes.
- 2) Reagent production, especially sodium hydroxide and MIL-101-Fe, is a substantial contributor to resource and emission burdens, highlighting opportunities for cleaner synthesis and reagent recovery.
- 3) Regional sensitivity analysis demonstrates the importance of contextualizing environmental performance within local energy infrastructures.
- 4) The integration of LCA results into system scale treatment assessments is critical for determining whether novel materials yield genuine environmental benefits.
- 5) The study provides a methodological basis for future work within IN2AQUAS, enabling the refinement of synthesis routes, scaling strategies, and sustainability benchmarks for emerging wastewater treatment technologies.

In conclusion, innovative materials hold the prospect of advancing wastewater treatment, but their development must be guided by life cycle thinking to ensure that efficiency gains translate into tangible sustainability improvements.

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